

Entitlement Racism on YouTube: White injury—the licence to Humiliate Roma migrants in the UK

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ABSTRACT

Hate speech monitoring has become a challenging task for social media platforms. While efforts have been made to combat racism and other forms of hate speech, marginalised communities, such as the Roma are frequent targets of intense discrimination and online racist abuse. This article examines manifestations of Romaphobia, also known as anti-Roma racism, on YouTube in the context of 2016 UK Referendum on EU membership, when Roma along with other Eastern European migrants became demonized in the right-wing narratives of Brexit supporters. Drawing on Thematic Analysis and Critical Discourse Analysis, the article provides an in-depth account of how Romaphobia is discursively constructed in the commentaries of those watching YouTube documentaries about Eastern European migrants. In addition to drawing attention to various forms of overt and covert racism that fly under the radar in the content moderation process, the analysis shows that ‘entitlement racism’ is gradually becoming normalised in social media, with anti-Roma racism acquiring alarming levels of verbal violence which needs immediate attention.

1. Introduction

Online racism is relatively an underexplored field of research which needs special attention, given the fact that social media often become sites for extreme verbal violence toward various marginalised groups (Matamoros-Fernández and Farkas, 2021). Scholarly work informs us that in post-race narratives, racism in institutionalised discourses, such as mainstream media or political discourse, primarily relies on colour blind ideologies (Bonilla-Silva, 2006), implying that the exclusion and marginalisation of minorities are not based on their race, but rather on socio-economic and/or cultural incompatibilities (Ang, Ho and Yeoh, 2022), or in the case of European Roma, also on their purported refusal to be part of the wider society (Breazu, 2020). Anti-Roma racism has a long history in Europe and the public discourse about Roma has been unchanged for centuries (Hancock, 2002), which justifies their precarious social status, extreme poverty, and large-scale violence against Roma in many parts of Europe (McGarry, 2017; Breazu and Machin, 2018). The proliferation of social media has opened up for new ways for racism to emerge and, thus, provides an opportunity to examine how online spaces shape racism and racist discourses. While colour-blindness is still the norm to express racist views, overt racism comes to surface, at

times in very extreme ways (Bonhomme and Alfaro, 2022; Breazu and Machin, 2023), which is worrisome and, therefore, cannot be overlooked. Social media have become venues where, under the guise of freedom of speech, people feel entitled to express their racist views (Ortiz, 2021) or possess ‘a license to humiliate others’ (Essed, 2013). Research shows that freedom of speech is indeed a pillar in right wing-ideology and has become part of the rallying cry of the far right in the culture wars in the UK and beyond (Holtz-Bacha, 2021). As we shall see in the analysis, social media, such as YouTube, which claim to value differences of opinion, have emerged as battleground for those wishing to advance racism, discrimination and other abusive behaviours.

YouTube, Facebook and Twitter rely on automated approaches to detect racism and other forms of hate speech, yet these technologies have some limitations, especially since they merely rely on classifying racist text using support word vector models for detecting racism (Burnap and Williams, 2015). Classifying racist text using support vector machines is a challenging task because words alone are insufficient indicators of racist views meaning that subtle forms of racist discourse (sarcasm, humour, or images) fly under the radar. Laaksonen et al. (2020) discuss the insidious example of ‘send them home’ in the context of immigration, which is a common example of hate speech encountered

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throughout my corpus. None of the words in this refrain is indicator of hate speech or racism; yet, together they reinforce exclusion of immigrants and even endorse violent actions, such as forcible deportations. Similar examples found in my corpus (e.g., ‘If only COVID could select people naturally’, ‘Norilsk is the answer, they should all go to Norilsk’) are not regarded as credible threats, although they clearly allude to extermination of Roma. The task of detecting online racism by AI technology is even more difficult because of the multimodal and cultural manifestations of racism (Breazu and Machin, 2019; Siapera, 2022), where racism is embedded in images, gifs, emojis, videos, various forms of typography and fonts. This requires researchers to assemble discourses expressed through various modes in order to show how racism operates in social media.

It is reasonable to question what makes racism more and more normalised in online spaces, especially during socio-political crises, such as Brexit (2016-) and why people feel a sense of entitlement to openly express their racist views in social media. This article focuses on YouTube, the largest video sharing platform, examining how users engage with controversial content about Roma migrants in the UK, content created and circulated by large media companies, such as UK-based Channel 5. Drawing on thematic analysis and multimodal critical discourse analysis, it shows how Romaphobia is increasingly normalised on social media, often in ways which remain largely unchallenged and where at times anger, frustration, sarcasm, irony and humor are important discursive strategies through which people engage in racist exchanges.

2. YouTube and Racism

As the largest search engine in the world, after Google, YouTube has dominated the internet video for almost two decades. Ever since it was purchased by Google, YouTube has expanded its business model from user-generated to professionally generated content, with an advertising revenue of over \$ 28.8 billion in 2021. Despite its gigantic success, YouTube has become under public scrutiny, being criticised for inconsistency in its Community Guidelines on Hate Speech and for failing to successfully monitor racism and other forms of discrimination (Hokka, 2021; Matamoros-Fernández, 2017).

As a neoliberal platform, YouTube encourages content creators to adopt a supply-demand perspective in order to compete for popularity and economic rewards (Munger and Phillips, 2022). This means that content creators may resort to contentious views, as long as these do not violate the values of the intimate community of subscribers. YouTube values are based on four essential freedoms: freedom of expression, freedom of information, freedom of opportunity and freedom to belong, with great emphasis on the freedom of expression: ‘we believe people should be able to speak freely, share opinions, foster open dialogue, and that creative freedom leads to new voices, formats and possibilities.’¹ This does not exclude the possibility for creators to publish content highlighting ‘contentious views’ which could in fact be racist, sexist or hateful toward various groups of people (Hokka, 2021). With over 500 h of content uploaded per minute, the moderation process becomes a rather challenging task both for AI technology and YouTube human moderators.

Research shows that contemporary racist discourses have become more subtle and disguised often relying on colorblind frameworks to dismiss accusation of racism (Bloch et al., 2020; Bonilla-Silva, 2006). This is certainly the case with the right wing-populist rhetoric in the UK, especially during Brexit where the exclusion of immigrants rarely alluded to their being ‘racially other’, but to their perceived incompatibility to live among the locals including supposed economic insufficiency, cultural otherness, criminality or the changes and chaos

they reportedly bring in the places where they migrate (Breazu and McGarry, 2023; Hughes, 2019). These views are often presented in ways which appear rational and justified, rather than as open prejudice, thus avoiding accusations of racism (Van Dijk, 2015).

One set of ideas used to mask this structural racism is rooted in an abstract notion of liberal meritocracy which legitimizes a discourse of ‘color-blindness’ (Bonilla-Silva, 2006). In this liberal view, all individuals have equal opportunities to work hard and achieve desirable forms of wealth, status, power and personal fulfilment. This colour-blind liberalism can be used to criticise and delegitimize policies, programs and initiatives which aim to reduce racial inequalities as it goes against this idea of meritocracy (Ben 2022; Bloch et al., 2020). Racial groups claiming the need for such special attention to address injustices can be dismissed as playing the ‘race card’ and seeking unearned advantages and privileges (Bonilla-Silva, 2006; Bloch et al., 2020). Colour-blind racism also creates a space for the conviction that whites or natives are constantly disadvantaged by governmental favouritism towards migrants and ethnic minorities—generating a sense of ‘white injury’ or ‘nativist victimhood’ and legitimizing the need to retain dominance (Bloch et al., 2020; Huber et al., 2008). This idea of ‘white injury’ or ‘nativist victimhood’ on social media in general, and YouTube in particular, trespasses the boundaries of colorblindness, making blunt forms of racist rhetoric increasingly socially accepted and normalised in online fora, with people having a sense of entitlement to be racist and humiliate others coming from various ethnic minority backgrounds (Ortiz, 2021; Essed, 2013). ‘Entitlement racism’ (Essed, 2013) is the practice of claiming the right to express racist views in the name of freedom of speech, a phenomenon which is increasingly normalised in social media. This is often attributed to the fact that there are no clear rules on how individuals should engage in dialogues in social media (Siapera, 2022), and, therefore, under the guise of anonymity and freedom of speech they claim the right to be racist. In addition, in the context of political crises, such as Brexit, ‘entitled’ racist attitudes were incited to a large extent by right-wing populist politicians and media who promoted ideas about British rights being constantly overlooked by the left and the EU, all these in favour of immigrants (Breazu and McGarry, 2023; Levinger, 2017). Thus, in the name of freedom of speech and of a perceived nativist victimhood, people feel that they have the right to display publicly and unapologetically their views on immigration and racial minorities.

One aspect that has been less explored in social media research is the role of humour and ridicule in upholding the norms and values of groups believed to be racially and culturally superior (Matamoros-Fernández et al., 2022). Scholars have highlighted that humour and ridicule serve concrete ideological functions in discourse in relation to ethnic minorities, such as to discipline minorities, to mark power, to set clear boundaries, cast judgement upon minorities, uphold norms and values or to humiliate groups believed to be culturally inferior (Billig, 2005; Pérez, 2017). Jokes about ethnic minorities often rely on stereotypical assumptions about the intelligence/rationality of the teller versus the stupidity/irrationality of the butt of joke (Weaver, 2011). Weaver (2011) also highlights that ‘the racial other’ is perceived as more ‘corporeal’, meaning that minorities are perceived as potentially indolent, lazy, purposeless and possibly criminal or defined by sexual immorality and excessive levels of reproduction. Humor on social media creates a space for like-minded people to bond together and vent common frustrations. As such, humor and ridicule are just convenient strategies to mask racism, at times substituting cruel, racist discourses for ones which appear to be playful, innocent and above all entertaining (Breazu, 2022; Sue and Golash-Boza, 2013).

This article examines how the general public engages with such content about Roma migrants published by Channel 5 in order to understand how YouTube viewers reproduce, reshape, reformulate, reject or contest the content laid out in these YouTube videos. It draws attention to various strategies by means of which racism flies under the radar on YouTube, showing how ‘entitlement racism’ (Essed, 2013) is

¹ YouTube Social Impact: Four essential freedoms that defines YouTube: <https://socialimpact.youtube.com/intl/en-GB/about/>.

increasingly normalised in social media (Ortiz, 2021), often taking extreme forms of verbal violence and dehumanization.

3. Data and method

The data presented here is part of a larger project on Romaphobia on YouTube. Data was collected using a custom developed PHP script through the YouTube API project, which allows identifying videos uploaded on YouTube by keywords, time frame, number of views, likes, dislikes and number of comments. It will be unrealistic to analyse all data in a single paper because of the large number of videos and comments. For this analysis I focus on a case study, 'Gypsies on Benefits and Proud' a documentary series uploaded on YouTube by the British Channel 5. I selected a documentary which sparked significant controversy because of its anti-immigration focus, received considerable coverage in UK mainstream media and generated over 5000 comments. Thematic analysis of YouTube comments was conducted using NVivo software. The process began with importing the comments, converted into an NVivo compatible format. After familiarisation with the data, a coding phase was initiated, assigning 'codes' or 'nodes' to represent themes within the data. These codes were then examined and organized to identify broader themes. The identified themes were reviewed and refined, ensuring an accurate representation of the data. The process culminated in visualising and reporting the findings using NVivo's mapping and exporting tools. This iterative analytical method allows researchers to revisit various stages to optimize understanding and exploration of the data.

This study employs a Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis (MCDA), following the tradition of Machin and Mayr (2023). It critically examines language and other modes of communication to show representations of individuals and events based on the principles of social semiotics outlined by Kress and Van Leeuwen (2001). This approach aids in examining both verbal and visual elements that shape discourses about the Roma community on a specific YouTube forum.

Discourses, defined as representational and interpretive world models (Van Leeuwen, 2008), comprise various elements like participants, social relations, actions, and values. According to Van Leeuwen (2008), these elements combine to form discursive scripts that depict actors performing actions within set contexts.

The study focuses on the concept of 'recontextualisation of social practice', exploring how social practices, particularly discourses about the Roma, are converted into context-specific representations. The analysis in this paper is conducted in relation to the 2016 UK referendum on EU membership, as criticism of Eastern European immigration and the EU's open border policies were central to pro-Brexit narratives.

This analysis employs Van Leeuwen's (2008) analytical inventory to identify which script components are omitted, added, or modified, and their related political agendas.

Common discursive transformations include substitutions, which impart new meanings by replacing concrete individuals and events with abstractions. Deletions are transformations that involve the removal or non-representation of various elements of the social practice. Additions refer to the process of augmenting elements to the social practice, 'enriching' the discourse with evaluative and moral dimensions. Rearrangements adjust the sequential order of events or elements to align with the various communication aims. Repetitions, recurrent patterns of expression, can serve to frame social and political discussions about specific groups. The role of visual elements (emojis and typography) in the recontextualisation process is also considered.

3.1. Context: Channel 5 documentary "Gypsies on Benefits"

This documentary originally aired on Channel 5 on 1 March 2016 and soon after it was published on YouTube is part of a series on immigrant stories and their experiences while living on benefits in the UK. The title of the documentary, 'Gypsies on Benefits,' brings with it a

range of problematic implications, stemming primarily from the derogatory use of the term 'Gypsies' as opposed to 'Roma/Romanies'. The term 'Gypsies' has often been used as a pejorative label; by tying the Roma community directly to 'benefits', the title reinforces prejudice and fuels misperceptions (Breazu, 2020; McGarry, 2017).

This particular documentary claims to give insights into the life of a Slovak Roma family which moved to the UK in search for a better life. The documentary is organised in sequences of humorous accounts of incompetence, stupidity and entitlement, highlighting how this couple with 11 children and 11 grandchildren exploit the British welfare system. The wife, who is said to have lived in the UK for seven years, has only worked for one month, and the husband, a builder by profession, has been out of work for two years. Despite being unemployed they seem to enjoy their new life in the UK, as they express in their limited English:

'England give me house, give me doctor, school, benefit. England good. Thank you so much England. Thank you very much.'

The anti-immigration stance of Channel 5 is obvious. We have no access to the editing techniques, or to how people were asked to perform for the casting, but the final product portrays a collective negative image of Roma migrants in the UK as shameless abusers of benefits. The way people act in front of the camera generates a mix of cheap laughter and frustration (as we shall see in the commentaries of social media users): the husband, a professional builder, shows his handyman skills while painting over mould and the wife appears to chain smoke and laugh hysterically while talking about her life in the UK. They also appear demanding, as they complain about the quality of the house they received from the government:

'In Slovakia, house is strong, you know. England no strong house.'

The woman's benefits were suspended because of her not actively looking for a job, yet she acts unreasonably as she states in her native Slovakian:

'It's not fair to suspend money like this.' 'Is it right to do that? No! Every time I go to sign on, they come up with something... all the time. I am so cross! So cross!'

Of course, such media discourses about immigrants from Eastern Europe is not neutral, especially in the context of the British Referendum on EU membership. Ever since Slovakia joined the EU in 2004, Slovakian migrants could work and live in the UK without restrictions. This was met with resistance both from UK politicians and wider society. The EU open-door immigration policy has been much criticised by Brexit supporters and such documentaries have fuelled anti-immigration sentiments and have served as evidence for the pitfalls of migration, especially from Eastern Europe (Radziwinowiczówna and Galasińska, 2021). As we shall see in the analysis, such media content published on YouTube opens up to new levels of racism and discrimination, which indeed situates Romaphobia as the 'last acceptable form of racism' (McGarry, 2017).

4. The analysis

4.1. Thematic analysis

One of the affordances of YouTube is that researchers can gain valuable insight into how people make sense of what they watch or read, even though this understanding is contextual and applies to particular case studies. The thorough coding of three sets of data, all in reference to documentaries about Roma in the UK point to the following common themes:

- (1) **Roma as the symbol for the "bad migrant"**: this is a dominant theme which includes references to Roma as savvy exploiters of the UK welfare system. Roma appear to know how to play the "race card" and get free handouts from a naive government which

seems to favor them. Roma migrants are perceived as unskilled and unproductive members of the society, unwilling to engage in conventional ways of earning a living, yet unappreciative and arrogant. This plays well in a socio-political context where unwanted migration from Eastern Europe has been a key argument in right-wing rhetoric of Brexit supporters (Radziwinowiczówna and Galasińska, 2021) and we see numerous commentators stating that Roma migration to the UK influenced their decision to vote to leave the EU.

- (2) **Roma as (Un)European:** this theme addresses the issue of belonging, with Roma cultural identity being regarded outside European membership. There are numerous accounts in the corpus where people see them as unSlovakian, unRomanian, unHungarian. Instead, Roma remain ‘the other (Un)Europeans’ inhabiting the state, yet outside the nation (McGarry, 2017). This is illustrated by constructing the Roma as a generic ‘type of people’ who possess a collective bad reputation and bring chaos everywhere they live or migrate. This is also evident in those polarised stories of what it means to be a good migrant.
- (3) **Extreme hate speech:** there is a sense that those posting compete for the ‘smartest’ comment, with the crudest and funniest comments generating most engagement and validation from the online community. We see accounts of extreme dehumanisation of Roma: emojis of excrements, vomit, abusive language invoking well-trodden stereotypes, as well as the endorsement of violence against Roma, including calls for ethnic cleansing/genocide. This discourse is often executed through sarcasm and humor, which euphemises violence and makes it look playful.
- (4) **Counter discourses:** there is a limited number of anti-racist discourses (151), with commenters raising awareness about the damaging effect of such documentaries aired by Channel 5, which only incite to more hatred and racism. Those posting counter discourses attempt to educate the general public with regards to the inflammatory hate speech generated by such media content. Yet, these efforts are not successful considering the backlash of negative comments.

The above brief thematic analysis, even though descriptive, gives insights into the inflammatory language used on YouTube to talk about Roma migrants in the UK. One common trait shared by these themes is that commentators rely on two main strategies to reproduce racist views: (1) racism embedded in populist and nativist rhetoric and (2) racism veiled under the guise of sarcasm, irony and humor. In what follows we shall examine each of these discursive strategies.

4.2. Racism embedded in populist and nativist rhetoric

In the context of Brexit, populist and nativist discourses were central in the right-wing rhetoric in favour of UK’s leaving the EU (Abranches et al., 2021; Virdee and McGeever, 2018). Thus, Roma as well as other Eastern European groups, were vilified both in media and political discourse as the undesirable migrants, scapegoated for the decline in the economic prosperity and the ‘loss’ of British national identity and autonomy (Breazu and McGarry, 2023). Populist and nativist rhetoric is a dangerous way through which racism can be overlooked, euphemised or simply dismissed (Mondon and Winter, 2020), especially since the exclusion of ethnic minorities appears to be based on economics, culture and values or social incompatibilities (Ang, Ho and Yeoh, 2022). Interestingly, commentators posting on this forum, point to these documentaries as evidence as to why they voted in favour of UK leaving the EU.

C1: *What a family of free loaders! They knew what they were doing when they migrated to the UK! At least Brexit will avoid this from continuing.*

C2: *This is the rich multicultural society that we live in. And of course when they reach retirement age they will get a pension, this is a result of being in the EU and having open borders. ☐.*

C3: *These people make my blood boil. Freeloaders of the worst kind come to the UK to take all they can with handouts.*

C4: *THIS IS WHY WE ALL VOTED OUT THE EUNo more!*

C5:

The documentary aired by Channel 5 is not explicitly racist, nor does it make reference to Brexit nor EU open border policy. However, the anti-immigration sentiment is obvious, and the way it is edited clearly invites negative feelings toward the Roma. In the above comments (C1-3), we see how the discourse is recontextualised in the commentaries of those posting by means of additions and substitutions (Van Leeuwen, 2008). Commentators add derogatory language (‘family of free loaders’, ‘Freeloaders of the worst kind’) to further dehumanise and stereotype Roma migrants as manipulative and opportunistic. The use of ‘rich multicultural society’ sarcastically conveys a disapproving stance towards immigration and the social changes it brings. By focusing on future entitlements (‘when they reach retirement age they will get a pension’, ‘take all they can with handouts’), the rationale behind Roma’s migration is substituted for financial gain, rather than poverty, discrimination and lack of opportunities. The use of all capitals letters (C4) symbolises shouting and strong populist sentiment. The discourse not only dehumanizes the Roma community, but it also frames Brexit as a corrective measure approved by the ordinary people (‘WE ALL VOTED OUT THE EU’) to stop Roma and other migrants from taking advantage of UK welfare system. The single family featured in this documentary becomes representative for all Roma, whose culture demands they live off British benefits. The comments on this forum are not directed specifically to this family but to ‘they’ the Roma, the symbol for the unwanted Eastern European migrants and evidence for how UK government mishandled immigration. This sense of injury gives people (both British and non-British) the entitlement to vent their frustration, anger and hostility toward the Roma (Essed, 2013; Essed and Muhr, 2018), which is also evident in the use of emojis (C2 & C5). Emojis, such as the face screaming in fear (😱), the nauseated face (🤢), the vomiting face (🤮), and the exploding head (💥), are often deployed in the comments section to amplify the anti-Roma sentiment. These symbols, while seemingly innocuous in isolation, become potent tools for spreading hate, especially in this particular context. The ‘exploding head’ emoji is used to mockingly overstate a reaction to Roma lifestyle or practices. Similarly, the ‘nauseated face’ and ‘vomiting face’ emojis subtly indicate users’ disdain or revulsion towards the Roma community.

C6: *Unbelievable!!! No wonder this country is bombarded with foreigners. Too soft handing out money we work hard for!! Fuming!!*

C7: *These people get benefits not because they are immigrants from Eastern Europe how everyone thinks, they get these benefits because they are racial minority.....they get better benefits than rest of the Slovaks too...except most of Slovaks work or actively look for a job as it is culturally an embarrassment to sit at home on benefits.*

C8: *I am Slovak, here in the UK and it makes my blood boil too. There go my taxes whether I am here or there. They have no dignity shamelessly taking advantage of the system. I hate to be associated with it.*

C9: *White East Europeans have no chance getting these benefits...this lot got it because they are romani. UK did this to themselves.*

The populist views underpinned in the documentary resonate well with the YouTube audience, as we see viewers/commentators taking the discourse to a higher level of hate speech. There is a strong populist emotional response from commentators with much anger and hostility directed toward the Roma. In the above comments we see a series of

additions to the discursive script laid out in the documentary, which further perpetuate harmful stereotypes and racialised narratives about Roma migrants. Commentators add emotive language (they make my blood boil', 'Fuming!!', 'Unbelievable!!!') to construct anti-Roma sentiment. These emotions appear to be legitimate and, therefore, a natural reaction of ordinary people (Hughes, 2019, Levinger, 2017), who feel dissatisfied with personal and economic well-being, while 'undeserving immigrants' such as Roma, appear to do well and be favoured by the government. This is a form of 'entitlement racism' (Essed, 2013), where racist attitudes are provoked by assumptions that Roma are privileged over British and white Eastern Europeans in the UK, feeding into a narrative of victimhood among white Eastern Europeans.

Apart from derogatory language used in reference to the Roma which runs all over this forum ('freeloaders', 'moochers', 'spongers', 'leeches') commentators on this YouTube forum do not shy away from expressing their hatred and as we shall see later it culminates with extreme calls for violence. There is a constant polarisation between the 'we' and "they", with "we" consisting of native Britons and other commentators who regard themselves as 'good/deserving migrants'. Roma are said to skilfully play the "race card" (Bloch et al., 2020) and always get away with free handouts ('claim benefits because they are a racial minority', 'claim benefits with impunity', 'take all they can with handouts', 'have no dignity shamelessly taking advantage of the system'). In addition, they are also blamed for ruining the chances of 'good migrants' who seek a better life in the UK ('most of Slovaks work or actively look for a job,' 'White East Europeans have no chance getting these benefits'). Interestingly, Eastern Europeans on this forum strive to disassociate themselves from Roma, especially since in right-wing rhetoric, Roma and other Eastern European migrants are perceived as a conflated category of unskilled and unwanted migrants (Breazu and McGarry, 2023). Several comments from Slovak nationals highlight this distancing as they align with the British in jointly criticizing the perceived manipulative and opportunistic nature of Roma. There is also an emerging narrative of nativist victimhood from British commentators who voice out their frustration with a system which seems out of touch with their needs and which apparently favour the Roma.

C10: *This is happening all over the country. If you're British get to the back of the cue*

C11: *The system doesn't benefit the natives who need it, so fair play to these people taking advantage of a rigged game!*

C12: *Infuriating! I work 2 jobs to help provide towards a family of just 3 and I'm livid that I pay tax to fund a family who does NOTHING to contribute towards society. Spongers.. no other word for it*

C13: *This really hurts my soul and I don't live in *

The above-mentioned comments (C10-13) serve as examples of how right-wing nativist rhetoric plays out among British commentators. In terms of recontextualisation here we can mention additions and abstractions (Van Leeuwen, 2008). These individuals add their personal frustration towards 'out of touch' political elites, accusing them of betraying the interests of native Britons by favouring immigrants, such as Roma. The disillusionment with the system is emphasised, suggesting the system is rigged against the natives ('If you're British get to the back of the cue,' 'The system doesn't benefit the natives who need it,' 'the taxpayers are footing the bill,' 'the system enables these free loaders they act so entitled'). Some commentators also externalize personal struggles ('I work 2 jobs...', 'I worked all my life...', 'I pay tax to fund a family who does NOTHING to contribute towards society') and project their anger onto Roma migrants, whom they view as non-contributing and exploitative ('spongers'). Such projections of anger are simple abstractions (Van Leeuwen, 2008), especially since they assume a direct correlation between their own hardship and the benefits that Roma

migrants receive, feeding into a narrative of 'entitlement racism'. There is a sense of loss of control, with British interests being neglected: the system doesn't benefit the natives while Roma are privileged and tax money is used to fund lazy Roma and their large families; people who worked hard receive low pensions, while Roma earn a living just from making babies. This type of nativist grievance refrains from outright racist slurs, yet it embodies, enacts and naturalises racism (Lentin, 2016). It amplifies a sense of great injustice, framing Roma as disrupters of social order and implying the need for corrective measures to revert to a glorified past (before Eastern European migrants were allowed in the country). As seen in these comments, this nativism becomes bound up with a notion of the native's rights. It suggests that migrants and ethnic minorities are manipulating the 'race card' (Bloch et al., 2020) to gain unearned privileges, thereby fueling nativist victimhood, and legitimizing the need to maintain dominance (Huber et al., 2008). The use of the angry face emoji () emphasizes the speaker's sympathy towards UK taxpayers.

C14: *Benefits should be stopped completely, and they should be sent back to their own country. If you don't pay into system you don't get out (scrounges) [REPLY 579]*

C15: *I agree, ship 'em off, this is our country*

C16: *Deport the scruffs*

C17: *We need to deport all foreigners that don't work full stop*

C18: *USELESS OXYGEN THIEVES!!*

C19: *There's no value with people like this. Pity they just don't die.*

C20: *if someone threw a petrol bomb through their window while they slept*

C21: *Go back to where you came from!!!!*

C22: *D-E-P-O-R-T-AT-I-O-N*

Comments 14–22 reveal an escalating aggression and hostility towards Roma. The language used by commentators is increasingly violent and dehumanising, reflecting augmented sentiments of xenophobia, nativism, and entitlement racism. All these comments explicitly demand expulsion of the Roma from the UK, focusing on the concept of paying into and benefitting from the system, indicating a belief in a deserved privilege for 'native' citizens. The use of possessive language ("our country") indicates a perception of entitlement to resources and space that should be protected from 'outsiders'. These comments further use dehumanising language, reducing the Roma to 'scruffs' and demanding their removal, emphasizing a perceived need for 'purification' of the space or even suggesting their death (C18-20). Such comments cross into the territory of promoting direct harm and violence against the Roma, (e.g., a petrol bomb attack). The usage of the UK () flag emojis indicates feelings of nationalism or patriotism, signaling that these countries should adopt stricter immigration policies.

Such interaction on social media is alarming, bearing a striking resemblance to fascist discourses—deportations, ethnic cleansing, calls for physical violence. What's more disconcerting is the transformation of these extreme sentiments into real actions against the Roma in several parts of Europe. This includes camp evictions and deportations in France, Italy and UK, travel bans, police brutality in Czech Republic, Romania, Bulgarian, Greece to name a few (as per reports from the European Roma Rights Centre²). This disturbing trend leads us to question why so many commentators brazenly endorse violent, racist

² European Roma Rights Centre is a Roma-led interest law organisation actively fighting anti-Roma racism and human rights abuse of Roma through strategic litigation, research and policy development, advocacy and human rights education <https://www.errc.org>.

phenomenon denotes the bond formed among likeminded individuals who collectively express their frustrations, in this case through humour.

Interestingly, the humour witnessed on this YouTube forum takes on a distinct gendered tone. References to the male subject's alleged hypersexuality are present, but he is seldom the target of vicious comments as the female character is. She bears the brunt of the abuse, with derogatory remarks targeting her femininity, appearance ('she is 43 but looks in her 60 s', 'she looks like a golem', 'she looks pregnant again', 'greasy hair', 'toothless', 'husky voice') and lifestyle choices ('smokes', 'has 11 children'). What's more concerning is the objectification of the underage daughters in the documentary. A commentator implies they could resort to adult content platforms like OnlyFans to earn money, indicating a disturbing trend of dehumanising and sexualising minors.

Noteworthy here is that colourblind racism progressively fades away and the overt racism comes to surface in a deeply disturbing manner. Under the guise of a morbid humour, people propose extreme solutions to 'Roma problem', which remind of fascist methods of ethnic cleansing, as we see in the next examples.

C43: *One way trip to India? [deportation]*

C44: *If only COVID could naturally select people [extermination]*

C45: *This is why there should be selected breeding. [zero growth population]*

The hate and disgust toward Roma are represented publicly and unapologetically and escalate beyond the 'go home' narrative, further suggesting sinister methods of ethnic extermination, clothed in a facade of dark humour. The suggestion that Roma should be sent on a 'one way trip to India' alludes to ethnic cleansing through deportation. The comment also implies the idea of Roma's non-white origins and therefore not belonging in Europe. The implications of C44 are even more disturbing. Wishing the COVID-19 pandemic to serve as a 'natural selector' against the Roma demonstrates an extreme, deadly form of xenophobia, suggesting the eradication of an entire ethnic group due to deep-rooted prejudices and stereotypes. C45, calls for 'selective breeding' – a stark display of eugenics that seeks to curb the growth of the Roma population, echoing the disturbing practices of history's most repressive regimes. Such views are unproblematically expressed, as we see people even finding them entertaining (hysterical laughing emojis, thumbs-up, likes). Similar rhetoric would likely not go unnoticed or unchallenged if aimed at a different ethnic group. As McGarry (2017) points out, Romaphobia remains, to this day, a tragically accepted form of racism.

5. Conclusion

This article draws attention to two strategies through which racism toward the Roma flies under the radar on YouTube, being undetectable by neither AI technology nor human moderators employed by YouTube. These forms are: (1) racism embedded in populist and nativist rhetoric and (2) racist jokes veiled under the guise of sarcasm, irony, and humor. While this research is contextual and addresses the case of Roma migrants during the UK Referendum on EU membership, it contributes to the existing discussion of how racism operates on YouTube, drawing attention that 'entitlement racism' (Essed, 2013) is unmistakably a huge concern in social media. Under the guise of freedom of speech, people feel they have a licence to humiliate others (Essed and Muhr, 2018), and we can clearly see this happening on this particular YouTube forum. Commentators display a sense of entitlement to publicly and unapologetically express racist behaviours and even endorse inhumane treatment and violence against Roma migrants. This YouTube commentary section has proven to be a hotbed of anti-Roma racism, expressed through the strategic interplay of language and visual elements such as typography and emojis. The findings reveal that emojis allow for the expression of emotions or attitudes in a succinct, visually striking manner, thus contributing to the reinforcement of anti-Roma

sentiments. They often act as emotional amplifiers, exaggerating the disdain or amusement expressed in the textual comments. Moreover, the simplicity and ubiquity of emojis can make these harmful sentiments seem innocuous or even humorous to some viewers, further normalising such discriminatory attitudes.

It is reasonable to question if AI alone could undertake tasks in detecting and flagging online racism or other forms of hate speech. As it emerges, current AI models for sentiment analysis, rumour detection or sarcasm detection are not properly equipped to detect racism embedded in visuals, in sarcasm or in populist rhetoric, and, therefore, input from human moderators is crucial. Yet as Siapera (2022) clearly points out, this requires social media platforms like YouTube to invest in training moderators in specialized knowledge about racism. Thus, the expertise of qualitative researchers working on various forms of text analysis or digital ethnographic methods is very valuable for training moderators to make better judgements as to what is racist content on social media and for AI experts to develop better technology for detecting racism or other forms of hate speech. Additionally, YouTube must issue clear, straightforward guidelines defining hate speech, particularly racism—in terms of both content creation and user interaction.

By adopting these measures, significant strides can be made towards reducing online hate speech and fostering a safer, more inclusive digital environment for all. The true test for societal progress is not just ceasing online hate speech, but eradicating the deep-rooted prejudice that feeds it. This takes us back to the reason why this research matters: Roma human rights. The path to change begins with dismantling these ingrained stereotypes and fostering an inclusive society that respects and honors human rights and dignity.

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